

Cooperative Model Predictive Control for Avoiding Critical Instants of Energy Resilience in Networked Microgrids

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Abstract

The recent international agreements signed by the majority of developed countries, such as those reached at the Climate Change Conferences in Paris'15 and Dubai'23, propose an increasingly rapid transition toward an energy ecosystem with a clear predominance of renewable energy in electrical power systems. The development of such ambitious energy programs should deal with the inherited stochasticity that renewable energy systems entail, which, when coupled with uncertainty about the capacity of the grid to maintain a power supply owing to increasing demands, decarbonization processes and the widespread closure of nuclear power plants, pose a serious threat to the normal functioning of energy systems. When combined with the escalation of armed conflicts that imply the loss of supply as a result of attacks or cyberattacks on power plants and distribution networks, it becomes clear that the current energy paradigm in which there is a centralized grid supplying numerous consumers, many of whom do not have their own generation capacity, must shift toward increasing the deployment of renewable-energy-based self-consumption facilities. The continuous advances toward a decentralized energy system of this nature will also lead to more cooperation, increasing the presence of energy communities with a great need to strengthen internal resilience as a sustaining factor.

Considering the challenging framework of smart grids and energy transition, Microgrids would appear to be the key technology for the aggregation of generation, load and energy storage systems, and a cornerstone with which to provide the resilience and flexibility required for this new renewable-energy-based scenario. In addition to the complexity of the microgrid control problem, the issue of resilience energy management also has to be considered, which refers to the ability to adapt and supply loads during a specified period after a disruptive event with a loss of grid supply.

This paper introduces an innovative method based on Model Predictive Control (MPC) techniques with the aim of enhancing resilience in microgrids by maximizing the energy surplus and reducing the aforementioned critical instants at which the capacity to feed loads is minimum in the case of power grid outages. The results obtained show that the proposed algorithm enhances the energy resilience in microgrids while the overall operational cost is optimized. A method with which to enhance the resilience of interconnected microgrids through cooperative optimization methods is also developed and validated.

Keywords: MPC, Resilience, Microgrid, Critical points, Energy surplus, Energy exchange.

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Nomenclature

C	Capacity (Wh)
CC	Capital Cost (€)
Cost	Hourly economic Cost (€/h)
Cycles	Number of life cycles
Hours	Number of life hours
I	Iteration
J	Cost Function
LOH	Level of Hydrogen (Nm^3)
m	Minimum possible value on the control platform
M	Maximum possible value on the control platform
P	Electrical power (W)
SOC	State of Charge ($p.u.$)
T_s	Sample Period
z	Electrical power formulated as MLD (Mixed logical dynamical) variable (W)
Γ	Energy price(€)
δ	on/off state
η	Efficiency ($p.u.$)
λ, Λ	Relative / absolute cost margin ($p.u.$)
σ	Logical variable start up state
ϑ	MLD power variation in degradation state (W)
χ	Logical degradation state
Υ	Energy surplus(Wh)

Subscripts or Superscripts:

bat	Battery
ch	Charge
$const$	Constraint
$crit$	Critical
cur	Curtailement
$degr$	Degradation
dis	Discharge
elz	Electrolyzer
$exch$	Exchange
fc	Fuel Cell
gen	Generation
$\langle i \rangle$	Iteration i
$load$	Load
$grid$	Main grid
NW	Network
pur	Purchase of energy
pv	Photovoltaic system
rem	Remaining power
res	Resilience
$sale$	Sale of energy
Υ	Surplus
wt	Wind turbine

1. Introduction

As evidenced in recent armed conflicts, the first facilities targeted have been transportation networks, water networks and,

of course, electric power supply networks. Despite the significantly increasing penetration of renewable energy into the global energy landscape, the existence of a mainly centralized power system means that any disruptive event, whether resulting from an attack, collateral damage, or even natural disasters, can lead to the loss of the power supply to large areas, and thereby pose a problem as regards sustaining critical systems [1], [2].

Renewable energy microgrids act as protective systems against such disruptive events, as long as resilience criteria is prioritized in their design and implementation [3], [4]. This makes it possible to assess cost and resilience parameters in order to determine the optimal time instants at which to exchange energy with the grid, along with managing the level of local storage, integrating hybrid Energy Storage Systems (ESS) and configuring P2P (Peer to peer) exchanges. In the current paradigm, governments', businesses' and citizens' interest in ensuring energy supply and self production have increased considerably, as any problem in either a centralized power plant or the distribution line could lead to a serious disruption in a large consumption area. The creation of an environment comprising interconnected autonomous energy islands would allow a better response to potential destruction or failures in any other part of the system, which would have an effect only at a local level [5].

The addition of hybrid ESS implies that the ability to provide service in unforeseen circumstances is significantly greater. Specifically, batteries and hydrogen-based ESS are of a complementary nature, with batteries having a superior power density ratio (meaning a faster transient response) and hydrogen proving to be far better in terms of energy density (meaning longer autonomy) [6]. Operational costs and degradation concerns for both technologies have also proven to be complementary, signifying that by combining both technologies, the autonomy of the microgrid during off-grid periods is enhanced, resulting in an appropriate transient response and reducing the physical space required for energy storage.

1.1. Literature Review

Microgrid control is currently a widely studied topic. The conception of the term appeared at the start of the millennium, with papers such as [7], in which a conceptual description of a microgrid and the problems associated with managing these systems are discussed.

However, the concept of resilience did not gain attention until recently [8]. Most works, such as [6] and [9], focus on studying the cost function modeling and calculating the optimal operating method within a disruption-free system. The execution of an economic scheduling of microgrids with ESS for their active participation in the electrical market is undertaken in [10], in which the lower bounds of the ESS capacity are set aside as a resilience mechanism. In [11], the procedure described in [10] is expanded with the inclusion of energy forecast uncertainties by incorporating a stochastic formulation of Model Predictive Control (MPC). In [12], a specific schedule for the microgrid is followed when proposing a real-time control system based on MPC techniques.

One exception to the aforementioned economic-only approach can be found in [13], in which uncertainties regarding generators and loads are introduced into the process of determining an optimal economic schedule for microgrids. Other pioneering approaches to microgrid resilience can be found in [3], [14], [15], and [16], in which resilience management techniques for microgrids are addressed. The topics discussed in other papers, meanwhile, range from smaller-scale system management [17], [18], to the introduction of ESS such as potential energy and flywheels [19], [20], or a review of the potential of ESS to enhance grid efficiency [21]. In [22], a strategy centered around resilience optimization is proposed by taking into consideration the feasibility of islanding during normal operation and the ability to ensure the survival of critical loads during emergency periods. Most of the aforementioned resilience-focused papers apply these techniques only to single microgrids connected to the main network, although in [23], [24], [25] and [26], networked microgrids are studied in order to enhance energy behavior.

The topic of integrating fault tolerant control techniques into the Energy Management Systems (EMS) of microgrids is covered in [27], [28], [29], and [30], while a particular microgrid design focused on robustness to windstorms is described in [31]. In [32], a study concerning restoration capability in microgrids is conducted using a spanning tree search strategy. The methodology presented in [33] offers a means to identify vulnerable components and ensure resilient operation in the presence of multiple disruptions within the microgrid.

Two broad categories of resilience can be identified in [34]: 1) infrastructure resilience and 2) operational resilience. Infrastructure resilience primarily focuses on the physical strength of the infrastructure of the power system (also known as robustness [35]), with the objective of resisting and minimizing susceptibility to damage caused by significant disruptions. Operational resilience, meanwhile, pertains to the continuity of operations, ensuring the availability of uninterrupted supply or generation, even during major events. However, in most cases, disruptions to supply are primarily owing to failures in the distribution system [23], and the implementation of resilience criteria in individual or interconnected microgrids therefore results in a significant reduction in the severity of these disruptive events.

First attempts to quantify energy resilience in microgrids were made thanks to the development of two criteria: survivability and criticality. The first descriptions of the former concept, which is related to supplying the maximum number of charges for a short period of time, appeared in [36] and [37], while the latter, which refers to the coverage of critical charges for as long as possible, was introduced in [13].

Techniques with which to manage resilience with cost function minimization have been published in [4], as an extension of the work by [12], in which the procedure is decomposed into several scenarios that are solved sequentially in order to ultimately obtain an optimal joint result. In [38], a new method employing sliding mode control is developed for islanded microgrids, while [39] provides a control method for interconnected multi-energy microgrids, taking into account the environmental impact.

With regard to resilient microgrids, the use of MPC, a type of control method with which a framework can be generated in order to solve multi-objective cost functions based on the integration of constraints, is highly adaptable to the issue of microgrids [4], [6], [40], [41] and is becoming a growing trend. Its stochastic formulation allows the efficient management of uncertainties in the generation and utilization of energy in microgrids that introduce heuristic variables into the control, which, owing to their participation in the electricity market, are challenging to resolve [42] [43]. In [44] [45] and [46], the application of predictive MPC to microgrids is considered, while in [6], the application is extended to a hybrid generation and storage MPC for the management of microgrids with access to the energy market. This topic is discussed extensively in [6] and in [12].

A graphical summary of the literature review presented in this section, along with the primary features of the proposed control methods, drawbacks and suggested improvements, can be found in Table 1.

1.2. Main Contributions

With regard to the state of the art of control algorithms for renewable energy microgrid systems, numerous studies focus on estimating the cost under normal operating conditions [6], [10], [12], [40], [45], but without considering criteria related to resilience. Network errors/failures, whether from a physical perspective (interruptions to the external power supply, the accidental disruption of cables during construction work, intrusions aiming to damage the facilities) or a software perspective (cyberattacks, control system and telecommunications failures), are so common that disregarding the potential occurrence of these events implies underestimating a significant portion of the inherent costs/risks associated with energy networks and, therefore, overestimating their economic benefit [4]. Furthermore, when considering that microgrid loads can be critical to the survival of the installation and/or personnel, as is the case of hospitals or military facilities, resilience adds substantial value and should, therefore, be given much more weight in the final cost results. These installations generally have a limited capacity for the distributed placement of energy generation and storage facilities, while needing to ensure high energy autonomy. It is consequently considered that the relevant literature does not cover the field of microgrid resilience to a sufficient extent.

The topic of hybridizing ESS has been addressed in certain works focused on improving cost [6], [11], [44]. However, the emphasis has not been placed on the potential use of these hybrid systems to enhance resilience. One exception to this trend can be found in [4], which proposes a multi-scenario method with which to determine minimum levels of stored energy in order to prevent critical-load supply failures, but without considering stochasticity in loads and generation for the definition of that minimum amount of energy.

The objective of this work is to improve microgrid resilience by identifying critical areas in which the resilience energy margin is at its lowest. It simultaneously explores new alternative operational strategies, while ensuring that the operational cost

is either maintained under strict excess margins or, ideally, improved. This approach also aims to reduce uncertainties associated with fluctuations in load demand and potential disruptions within the power generation system through the introduction of a surplus of stored energy not covered in the method presented in [4].

The study provides a crucial insight by showcasing that increasing storage capacity does not necessarily result in elevated operating costs. The proposed algorithm introduces several remarkable features that can be considered the primary highlights of this study. These features encompass a holistic approach to optimizing the EMS, striving to achieve a balance between operational and economic efficiency and resilience under various iterations. The paper provides a robust framework in which to enhance energy management and microgrid operation, providing a solution to the increasing demand for resilient and efficient power systems and adaptability.

In order to attain these objectives, this paper builds upon the foundations laid by previous studies shown in [4], [10] and [11]. An innovative methodology for the determination of minimum resilience energy values is, therefore, introduced in which resilience parameters are integrated into the cost function, ultimately enhancing the outcome of the optimization process. This research also addresses the transition from grid-connected to islanded mode at any instant k within the day-ahead schedule, underpinned by the establishment of minimum energy criteria obtained through the integration of a 24+24 hours consumption profile, with a keen focus on solving the inherent uncertainty by maximizing the minimum surplus energy ν stored above said profile. This approach effectively renders the capacity of the system to adapt to uncertainties directly proportionate to the minimum value of Υ .

The most noteworthy features of the proposed algorithm, which constitute the primary highlights of this study, comprise:

- The development of an estimation of the minimum energy profile required in order to achieve resilience criteria, thus ensuring the provision of power to critical loads throughout an entire 24h period after the disruptive event, while considering the normal operation of the microgrid in grid-connected mode.
- The creation of an algorithm that performs an assessment of the available energy surplus Υ within the system by comparing the energy stored in the ESS (batteries and hydrogen) with the energy required to sustain loads throughout the estimated time span. This evaluation takes into account the potential transition to islanded mode at each sampling instance within the schedule horizon considered (SH)
- The calculation, storage and weighting of minimum resilience points, described as the minimum value of Υ for the SH , thus allowing the algorithm to enhance the margin by integrating "Min Υ " as a new decision variable, while providing a similar end cost result, within strict margins.
- After changing to a system of several microgrids that are

capable of exchanging energy with each other, the algorithm is formulated in order to determine how the energy exchanged can help soften those critical points and/or improve the cost studied for the independent work mode.

Table 1 provides a summary of the different characteristics integrated into the controller developed in this paper and compares them to those in the existing literature, highlighting the main features, drawbacks and possible improvements of each contribution.

1.3. Structure and Organization of the Paper

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 details the formulation of the proposed controller, while Section 3 discusses the key findings achieved with the proposed controller. Lastly, Section 4 outlines the conclusions of the work carried out.

2. Distributed MPC-based to Resilience Enhancement by employing Interconnected Working Mode of Microgrids

The microgrid (μg) studied herein is shown in Fig. 1. As can be seen, it is composed of wind turbines and photovoltaic generators, it contains critical and non-critical loads and there are two kinds of ESS: batteries and hydrogen.

In order to ensure the minimum operational capacity of the installation, critical loads have been established, which can be described as a portion of the overall standard load that cannot be ignored. Unlike the other loads, these systems ensure the well-being of personnel, communications or the minimum requirements to keep the facility operational, and have to be supplied. Taking a military base as an example, we could mention the headquarters, and communications, defense and support facilities.

The normal operation mode will be connected to the main grid, and the calculations will subsequently refer to this situation. An islanded operating mode will be considered as the after-disruption event operating mode, and will be understood as a partially deterministic situation in which the total energy to supply after an event will be defined by the application of the survivability and criticality criteria that will be explained in the following subsection. Stochasticity will be introduced through the creation of an optimization variable Υ , which will determine how the system can overcome unforeseen overload events by amplifying the estimated levels of stored energy.

The controller system will consist of a prediction module, the plant model, the Economic MPC controller, and the Resilience MPC controller, as shown in Fig. 2. Each module will be explained at greater length in the relevant subsection.

2.1. General Terms and Design Criteria

The controller is designed in such a way as to allow the microgrid to participate in the Day-Ahead Market, and the sample time considered is, therefore, $T_s = 1$ hour, and is based on the ideas detailed below:

Table 1: Summary of features and drawbacks of, and suggested enhancements to the main papers on microgrids reviewed when compared to the controller proposed herein

Feature	[3] [8] [14] - [16] [27] - [29]	[6] [10] [12] [40]	[13] [33]	[11] [44] - [46]	[4] [39] [41]	Proposed method
Microgrid Resilience	✓		✓		✓	✓
Grid Energy Exchange		✓		✓	✓	✓
Survivability of loads			✓		✓	✓
Hybrid ESS		✓		✓	✓	✓
ESS Degradation Cost		✓			✓	✓
EMS Fault Tolerance Control	✓					
Cost optimization		✓		✓	✓	✓
Multi-scenario					✓(Just [4])	
Iterative procedure						✓
Energy surplus (Υ)						✓
Critical instant optimization						✓
Main drawbacks	Does not provide a developed hybrid ESS controller	Focused only on economical optimization aspects	Refers only to a single microgrid	Does not cover resilience & degradation issues	Does not cover generation stochasticity issues	Computational and technical complexity
Suggested enhancements	Developing a hybrid model using the proposed method	Application of resilience techniques	Considering introducing interconnected μ_g exchange	Application of resilience & degradation techniques	Taking into consideration energy flexibility	Automatization & improvement of the iterative procedure

1. *Resilience Criteria*: Two resilience criteria have been incorporated when creating the critical load profile: Criticality, which assesses the capability of the system to sustain critical loads for a duration comparable to that of the SH , and survivability, which gauges the ability of the system to power as many loads as possible for a brief period. [3],[13]. In the scope of this study, the criticality criterion has been set at a 24-hour threshold. However, our survivability criterion is narrowed down to the two hours immediately after the transition of the microgrid to islanded mode, a timeframe aligned with the customary duration required for electricity distribution companies to restore service. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the survivability or criticality timeframes are potentially extensible by following the same methodology, albeit at the trade-off of incurring heightened final costs.
2. *Minimum operational cost*: The objective of this study is not only to show the integration of resilience, but also to illustrate that an enhancement of this nature is not at odds with preserving the ultimate cost. This cost includes both

the procurement of system components and their amortization, which is attributable to degradation and potential failures, thereby ensuring that the outcome authentically captures the total cost, as presented in [10], [12].

3. *Surplus energy Υ* : As shown in [4], resilience can be defined as the amount of energy stored in the different ESS, meaning the state of charge (SOC) of the batteries and the level of hydrogen (LOH) in the tank. Our study is focused on enhancing the minimum values of surplus energy (Υ), an innovative parameter defined as the difference, at each time instant k in the SH , between the stored energy and the energy required to meet the survivability and criticality criteria. The critical resilience instant will, therefore, be defined as the period k of the SH in which this surplus Υ is lower.

2.2. Generic Assumptions and Theoretical Aspects of the Controller

The primary objective of the controller is to establish a procedure with which to enhance critical resilience energy instants in

Figure 1: Microgrid diagram considered in this paper

networked microgrids, understanding energy resilience as the autonomy conferred by its energy storage system state. This self-sufficiency can be allocated to the entire array of local loads or selectively reserved for critical ones, as exemplified in [4].

When microgrids function as a network, it is typical for the global cost function to be formulated by aggregating local objective functions, commonly designed to optimize economic criteria. The collaborative operation of multiple microgrids within a power network introduces an additional level of flexibility, leading to improved optimization results when compared to optimizing each microgrid separately.

However, the global objective may be defined for a purpose other than that employed for local optimization, such as enhancing the energy resilience of the microgrid network. The flexibility gained by means of energy exchange among microgrids allows the separate optimization of their economic costs while increasing stored energy. Moreover, it may be beneficial not to uniformly increase the amount of stored energy at all time points. Prioritizing critical instances, defined as sample periods with the lowest energy surplus, is also a possibility.

The local optimization problem for microgrid (i) in the MLD framework involves a set of sample instances k within a scheduling horizon SH and a sample period T_s . It can be defined as a cost function (1) that needs to be minimized [6],

subject to constraints (2)-(9).

$$\min J_i = J_i(\mathbf{u}_i, \delta_i) \quad (1)$$

Where the minimum and maximum values of the different variables are controlled as:

$$\mathbf{u}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}(k) \leq \mathbf{u}^{\max} \quad (2)$$

$$0 \leq \delta(k) \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

$$0 \leq \mathbf{z}(k) \leq \mathbf{z}^{\max} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{x}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{x}(k) \leq \mathbf{x}^{\max} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{y}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{y}(k) \leq \mathbf{y}^{\max} \quad (6)$$

Correlated in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k+1) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{B}_u\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{B}_\delta\delta(k) \\ &+ \mathbf{B}_z\mathbf{z}(k) + \mathbf{B}_d\mathbf{d}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}(k) &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{D}_u\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{D}_\delta\delta(k) \\ &+ \mathbf{D}_z\mathbf{z}(k) + \mathbf{D}_d\mathbf{d}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_\delta\delta(k) + \mathbf{E}_z\mathbf{z}(k) \leq \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{E}_u\mathbf{u}(k) + \mathbf{E}_d\mathbf{d}(k) \quad (9)$$

The procedure above is based on the work of [10], with Matrices A , B , C , D , and E being used to establish the foundation for the state space representation of the microgrid, δ being the logic or digital decision variables, \mathbf{z} being the mixed product

Figure 2: Block Diagram of the MPC

control variables of δ and \mathbf{u} , and \mathbf{x} representing the state variables of the plant model.

However, the continuous or analog decision variables \mathbf{u} are modified in order to introduce the new decision variables ($\Upsilon, \Upsilon^{crit}$):

$$\mathbf{u}^{<i>} = [P_{ch}^{<i>}, P_{dis}^{<i>}, P_{elz}^{<i>}, P_{fc}^{<i>}, P_{pur}^{<i>}, P_{sale}^{<i>}, \Upsilon^{<i>}, \Upsilon^{crit, <i>}]^T \quad (10)$$

where $P_{ch}^{<i>}$ and $P_{dis}^{<i>}$ are positive-only set points for the charging and discharging of the batteries, respectively, $P_{elz}^{<i>}$ and $P_{fc}^{<i>}$ are the reference power values for the electrolyzer and fuel cell, respectively, and $P_{pur}^{<i>}$ and $P_{sale}^{<i>}$ are also positive-only variables that are used to calculate the power exchange with the main grid during the selling and purchasing processes. Υ refers to the positive-only decision variable for the surplus energy, as will be explained in (33), while $\Upsilon^{crit, <i>}$ is a free parameter that stores the minimum value of Υ for the current iteration, as is described in greater detail in (37).

If the physical problem is to be transformed into a control model, it is essential to meticulously model each component of the setup, including its costs and operational challenges. This entails transforming the ESS (encompassing the batteries and hydrogen), the electrolyzer, and the fuel cell into logical en-

tities. This enables the solver to allocate states and costs dynamically to each system within the program, thus facilitating efficient management and optimization.

With regard to the ESS, the cost associated with battery usage comprises the influence of the frequency of charging/discharging cycles and the longevity of batteries. These factors are incorporated into the cost function by means of the manufacturer-guaranteed number of life cycles ($Cycles_{bat}$) and the parameter CC_{bat} , representing the initial capital cost of battery acquisition. As prolonged exposure to high-stress charging/discharging currents during continuous battery operation can diminish its lifespan, this leads to a quadratic penalty on the charging and discharging power, making the controller less prone to incurring it, as highlighted in [4].

While the hydrogen ESS also entails two distinct costs, its lifespan is not measured in operational cycles as occurs with other ESS types. It is rather evaluated on the basis of operating hours and the associated operation and maintenance costs, which are represented by the parameter $Cost_{o\&m}$, where $\delta_\alpha = 1$ signifies instances at which either the fuel cell or the electrolyzer is operational. Degradation costs in this context are influenced by two factors, as outlined in [10]: degradation processes associated with start-up/shut-down, denoted by

σ_α , which represents the initial state of the electrolyzer and fuel cell, and degradation costs arising from power fluctuations ϑ_α , which are applied to these devices during active periods, excluding instances of power state transitions. The controller must take into account constraints that are relevant to the microgrid's state space, as detailed in (7), (8), and (9).

Electrolyzers and fuel cells have three different degradation aspects that have to be considered in the model: operating range, start-down and shut-down cycles, and power fluctuation [10].

As operating electrolyzers and fuel cells at a power range ranging from 0% to 10% of their maximum capacity can severely damage their components, both fuel cells and electrolyzers are represented using a combination of logical and continuous variables $(\delta_\alpha, P_\alpha)$, where $z_\alpha = P_\alpha \cdot \delta_\alpha$. The deterioration undergone by the electrolyzer and fuel cell as a result of start-up and shut-down cycles is quantified within the controller through the use of auxiliary logic variables $\sigma_\alpha(t)$, while power fluctuations during their active periods, except during the startup and shutdown phases, are incorporated into the controller through the use of the mixed variable ϑ_α .

Weighting factors, which allow the controller to assess the specific economic parameters outlined in the methodology cited in references [4], [10], including device capital costs and lifespans, are intertwined with the new resilience parameters, such as w_Υ , which will be described in greater detail in Section 2.6, and are incorporated into the cost calculation with the values presented in Table 2. Parameters w_{SOC} and w_{LOH} , which weigh the storage in different ESS, are adjusted after determining the remaining weights, as they represent the most constraining criteria in the cost function, along with the aforementioned w_Υ , since it is imperative to ensure that all loads are supplied before any outage occurs.

In order to ensure that a minimum energy capacity threshold E_{res} in the ESS is maintained, a dynamical lower limit is defined using the expression (31). Two new variables Υ and Υ^{crit} have similarly been generated, as stated in (33), (37). The system will, therefore, together with the w_Υ parameter in (45), which has a value of $w_\Upsilon < 0$, prioritize the storage of the surplus of energy at the critical instants. A dynamic tracking of the minimum value of the array Υ , Υ^{crit} , has been designed using the model constraint presented in (38) in conjunction with w_Υ .

The equation presented in (9) is achieved by following the methodology outlined in [47] to transform the logical relationships among the variables \mathbf{u} , δ , and \mathbf{z} , owing to the presence of both continuous and logical variables. The initial states of start-up, $\sigma_{elz}^{<i>}$ and $\sigma_{fc}^{<i>}$ can be associated with $\delta_{elz}^{<i>}$ and $\delta_{fc}^{<i>}$, respectively, by employing the logical relationships depicted in (11). These relationships can subsequently be linearized as constraints using the expressions (12)-(14).

$$\sigma_\alpha^{<i>}(k) = \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \wedge \sim \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k-1)|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (11)$$

$$m \leq -\delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) + \sigma_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 0|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (12)$$

$$m \leq -(1 - \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k-1)) + \sigma_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 0|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (13)$$

$$m \leq \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) + (1 - \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k-1)) - \sigma_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 1|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (14)$$

Symbols \wedge and \sim represent, respectively, the logic operations AND and NOT. The relation between $\chi_{elz}(t)$ and $\delta_{elz}(t)$ is defined in (15), introduced into the controller using the (16)-(18) constraints:

$$\chi_\alpha^{<i>}(k) = \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \wedge \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k-1)|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (15)$$

$$m \leq -\delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) + \chi_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 0|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (16)$$

$$m \leq -\delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k-1) + \chi_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 0|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (17)$$

$$m \leq \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) + \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k-1) - \chi_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 1|_{\alpha=elz,fc} \quad (18)$$

$$z_\alpha^{<i>}(k) = P_\beta^{<i>}(k) \cdot \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \quad (19)$$

$$m \leq z_\alpha(k) - P_\alpha^{max} \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 0 \quad (20)$$

$$0 \leq z_\alpha^{<i>}(k) - P_\alpha^{min} \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq M \quad (21)$$

$$P_\beta^{<i>}(k) - P_\alpha^{max}(1 - \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k)) - z_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \leq 0 \quad (22)$$

$$0 \leq P_\alpha^{<i>}(k) - P_\alpha^{min}(1 - \delta_\alpha^{<i>}(k)) - z_\alpha^{<i>}(k) \quad (23)$$

$$0 \leq \delta_\alpha + \delta_\beta \leq 1|_{\substack{\alpha=elz,fc \\ \alpha=dis,ch}} \quad (24)$$

Mixed products associated with the charging and discharging operations of the ESS can be defined using the mixed product outlined in (19). These can subsequently be transformed into linear constraints, as specified in (20)-(23), by substituting $\alpha = \{elz, fc, ch, dis\}$ and $\beta = \{elz, fc, bat, bat\}$, for $P_\alpha^{max} = -P_{bat}^{min}$, $P_{dis}^{max} = P_{bat}^{max}$, and $P_{ch}^{min} = P_{dis}^{min} = 0$. Here, m and M denote the minimum and maximum feasible values on the controller. In order to prevent inadequate energy processes such as charging the batteries through the fuel cell or electrolyzer hydrogen production via battery discharge, constraints in (24) are also introduced.

The mixed product defined as $\vartheta_\alpha(t)$, shown in (25), is eventually integrated into the controller using the linear constraints provided in (26)-(29), where $\alpha = \{elz, fc\}$.

$$\vartheta_\alpha(k) = (P_\alpha(k) - P_\alpha(k-1)) \cdot \chi_\alpha(k) \quad (25)$$

$$m \leq \vartheta_\alpha(k) - \Delta P_\alpha^{max} \chi_\alpha(k) \leq 0 \quad (26)$$

$$0 \leq \vartheta_\alpha(k) - \Delta P_\alpha^{min} \chi_\alpha(k) \leq M \quad (27)$$

$$m \leq \vartheta_\alpha(k) - \Delta P_\alpha(k) + \Delta P_\alpha^{min}(1 - \chi_\alpha(k)) \leq 0 \quad (28)$$

$$0 \leq \vartheta_\alpha(k) - \Delta P_\alpha(k) + \Delta P_\alpha^{max}(1 - \chi_\alpha(k)) \leq M \quad (29)$$

Note that, while the Resilience MPC Controller prioritizes ensuring system autonomy for critical loads and meeting survivability criteria within its cost function, the Economic MPC Controller is primarily focused on maximizing revenue through active participation in the Day-Ahead Market. These controllers have consequently been designed as separate and opposing control solutions, each tailored to address specific control objectives, characterized by unique cost functions and constraints. The final outcome will be determined by the importance assigned to the weight parameters, which can and will be adjusted so as to strike a balance between the final cost and the emphasis on resilience.

In the case of the networked operation mode, the optimization problem that considers the MLD framework can be defined as a Distributed MPC controller with global cost function J_{NW} for the network of microgrids and a local cost function J_i ,

where subindex NW represents the network of microgrids and the subindex i is used in order to refer to the microgrid i . When considering a pair of microgrids i and j , the global optimization problem can be defined with the expression (30) in which, the cooperation among systems makes it possible to find a most advantageous operation point compared to working as single systems :

$$\min J_{NW} = J_{NW}(\mathbf{u}_i, \delta_i, \mathbf{u}_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{v}_{i \rightarrow j}) \quad (30)$$

where the exchange variables between the microgrid i and its neighboring microgrid j are represented using $\mathbf{v}_{i \rightarrow j}$.

2.3. Particularization for the case of study

With regard to the study of microgrids with hybrid ESS composed of hydrogen and batteries, the local problem for the microgrids is defined by following the methodology of [4]. A consumption profile has been established for every hour of the SH , stating the minimum energy that should be stored in order to fulfill the required loads. Rather than sampling all 24 scenarios and considering a disconnection event at every single instant k , this model forecasts the total loads that have to be supplied, thus guaranteeing the coverage of these loads at any instant during the time schedule by means of the integration of the survivability and criticality criteria.

According to the methodology introduced in [4], the resilience level of a microgrid E_{RES} is a function of the energy stored in the different ESS integrated into the microgrid. The minimum amount of energy required in order to ensure the supply to critical loads E_{CRIT} is, therefore, explained by the resilience criteria. Since our proposed microgrid is composed of batteries and hydrogen ESS, these concepts can be defined in (31) for a given instant k of the SH , considering ν_{dis} as the efficiency for the discharge of the batteries, and $Cons_{fc}$ as the performance ratio of the fuel cell.

$$E_{RES}^{<i>}[k] = \underbrace{SOC^{<i>}(k) \cdot C_{bat} \cdot \nu_{dis} + LOH^{<i>}(k) / Cons_{fc}}_{Resilience\ Energy} \quad (31)$$

$$E_{CRIT}^{<i>}(k) = \underbrace{\sum_{n=k}^{k+1} P_{load}^{<i>}(n) \cdot T_S}_{Survivability\ Criterion} - \underbrace{\sum_{n=k}^{k+SH-1} P_{crit}^{<i>}(n) \cdot T_S}_{Criticality\ Criterion} \quad (32)$$

However, as the resilience energy E_{RES} defined in (32) does not exactly match the minimum amount of energy required in order to fulfill the survivability and criticality criteria E_{CRIT} for every k , a new variable with which to define the surplus of stored energy must be introduced (33).

$$\Upsilon^{<i>}(k) = E_{RES}^{<i>}(k) - E_{CRIT}^{<i>}(k) \quad (33)$$

being the upper and lower limits of this variable:

$$0 \leq \Upsilon \leq Max\ E_{RES} \quad (34)$$

The global problem defined in (30) can be particularized for the case study of enhancing the energy surplus through the use

of the interconnected operation mode of a pair of microgrids α_1 and α_2 as follows:

$$\min J_{NW}^{<i>} = -w_{\Upsilon}^{<i>} \left(\Upsilon_{\alpha_1}^{crit, <i>}, \Upsilon_{\alpha_2}^{crit, <i>} \right) + J_i^{<i>}(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha_1, global}, \delta_{\alpha_1, global}) + J_j^{<i>}(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha_2, global}, \delta_{\alpha_2, global}) \quad (35)$$

where Υ_{α}^{crit} is defined in (37) as the minimum point of Υ for the whole SH . Flexibility margins associated with economic losses with which to enhance the resilience are introduced by applying (36) for $\alpha = \alpha_1, \alpha_2$.

$$\frac{J_{\alpha}^{<i>}(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha, global}, \delta_{\alpha, global})}{J_{\alpha}^{<i>}(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha, local}, \delta_{\alpha, local})} \leq \lambda_{\alpha} \quad (36)$$

where λ is the flexibility coefficient that enables small cost deviations to allow an improvement to iterative resilience within strict cost increase margins.

Note that in the cost function (35), $\Upsilon_{\alpha}(k)$ is not optimized for all the sample instants, but only for the sample instant k_{α}^{crit} (37) of the schedule horizon SH , where the value obtained for Υ is the lowest (Υ^{crit}). This implies that the amount of stored energy is closer to the energy required in order to convey the resilience criteria, as defined in (37), constrained by (38). Also note that the notation indicates that the critical instants $k_{\alpha}^{crit, <i>}$ vary depending on the iteration $<i>$.

$$k_{\alpha}^{crit, <i>} \rightarrow \Upsilon_{\alpha}^{crit, <i>} = \min(E_{RES_{\alpha}}^{<i>}(k) - E_{CRIT_{\alpha}}^{<i>}(k)) \quad (37)$$

$$0 < \Upsilon_{\alpha}^{<i>}(k) - \Upsilon_{\alpha}^{crit, <i>} < Max\ E_{RES_{\alpha}} \quad \forall k \quad (38)$$

This procedure is iteratively applied until $OPT^{<i>}$ is found:

$$OPT^{<i>} = [\mathbf{u}_{\alpha_1, global}^{<i>}, \delta_{\alpha_1, global}^{<i>}, \mathbf{u}_{\alpha_2, global}^{<i>}, \delta_{\alpha_2, global}^{<i>}, \mathbf{v}_{\alpha_1 \rightarrow \alpha_2}^{<i>}] \quad (39)$$

The worst case scenarios are, therefore, covered by maximizing the value of Υ . This method provides the enhancement of the adaptability of this system, which can easily cover more than the calculated critical and non critical charge profile owing to the enhanced surplus.

2.4. Forecast Module

The prediction of the disturbance array \mathbf{d} (40) is carried out by the Forecast Module of the controller using the methodology defined in [10].

$$\mathbf{d} = [\hat{P}_{pv}, \hat{P}_{wt}, \hat{P}_{load}, \hat{P}_{crit}]^k \quad (40)$$

where the energy generation forecasted for the photovoltaic and wind turbine generators is defined by $\hat{P}_{pv}(k)$ and $\hat{P}_{wt}(k)$, respectively, and the consumption in the microgrid is provided by $\hat{P}_{load}(k)$ and $\hat{P}_{crit}(k)$, which are respectively defined as the total loads to supply in normal mode and the critical loads to supply after a disruptive event, in order to comply with the resilience criteria established.

The energy remaining, meaning the excess or defect of energy generated compared to that consumed at any period k of the SH , can be found as follows:

$$\hat{E}_{rem}(k) = \hat{P}_{pv}(k) + \hat{P}_{wt}(k) - \hat{P}_{load}(k) \quad (41)$$

The disconnection of non-critical loads during a fault occurrence is simulated by determining a critical load profile on the basis of the resilience criteria established and including it in the calculation of the minimum stored energy. This makes it possible to estimate the required minimum energy that should be stored and, therefore, the energy surplus Υ stored by the system.

2.5. Economic MPC-Controller Block

The results obtained from the Forecast Module shown above are used by the Economic MPC block to determine the minimum values for the state variables \mathbf{x} (considering the constraints (5)). To simplify, the uncertainties of the energy forecast are not taken into account, although this can be done by following the procedure outlined in [11]. In the Resilience MPC, each iteration calculates a value for LOH and SOC for each sample instant, which is dependent on the value of the variable in the previous instant and the energy stored or retrieved, along with its corresponding performance coefficient. The superindex $\langle i \rangle$ of each element indicates the iteration, while the subindex refers to the time instant of the SH considered.

$$LOH_{const} = \begin{bmatrix} LOH_1^{[1]} & LOH_1^{[2]} & \dots & LOH_1^{[i]} \\ LOH_2^{[1]} & LOH_2^{[2]} & \dots & LOH_2^{[i]} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ LOH_{SH}^{[1]} & LOH_{SH}^{[2]} & \dots & LOH_{SH}^{[i]} \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

$$SOC_{const} = \begin{bmatrix} SOC_1^{[1]} & SOC_1^{[2]} & \dots & SOC_1^{[i]} \\ SOC_2^{[1]} & SOC_2^{[2]} & \dots & SOC_2^{[i]} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ SOC_{SH}^{[1]} & SOC_{SH}^{[2]} & \dots & SOC_{SH}^{[i]} \end{bmatrix} \quad (43)$$

The LOH and SOC arrays obtained in (42)-(43) for each iteration will be the key aspects as regards obtaining the desired prediction in this part of the algorithm. In this case, the Economic MPC has only SH hours of the schedule horizon and the LOH and SOC constraint matrices therefore have a dimension of $SH \times i$.

The cost function of this control block is shown in (44).

$$J_{NoRes}^{\langle i \rangle} = \sum_{k=1}^{SH} \underbrace{\left(-\Gamma_{sale}^{DM}(k) \cdot z_{sale}^{\langle i \rangle}(k) + \Gamma_{pur}^{DM}(k) \cdot z_{pur}^{\langle i \rangle}(k) \right)}_{\text{Grid Exchange Revenue \& Cost}(J_{grid})} \quad (44)$$

$$+ \underbrace{\frac{CC_{bat}}{2 \cdot Cycles_{bat}} \sum_{\alpha=ch,dis} (z_{bat,\alpha}^{\langle i \rangle}(k))}_{\text{Batteries Cycling Cost}}$$

$$+ \underbrace{\sum_{\alpha=ch,dis} (Cost_{degr,\alpha} \cdot (z_{bat,\alpha}^{\langle i \rangle}(k))^2)}_{\text{Batteries ESS Degradation}}$$

$$+ \underbrace{\sum_{\alpha=elz,fc} \left(\left(\frac{CC_{\alpha}}{Hours_{\alpha}} + Cost_{o\&m,\alpha} \right) \delta_{\alpha}^{\langle i \rangle}(k) \right)}_{\text{Hydrogen ESS Hourly Cost Use}}$$

$$+ \underbrace{Cost_{startup,\alpha} \cdot \sigma_{\alpha}^{\langle i \rangle}(k) + Cost_{degr,\alpha} \cdot (\vartheta_{\alpha}^{\langle i \rangle}(k))^2}_{\text{Hydrogen ESS Degradation}}$$

The cost function (44) takes into account the potential for energy purchase or sale ($\Gamma_{pur}(k)$ and $\Gamma_{sale}(k)$, respectively), allowing energy exchange with the main grid at every sample instant. The primary goal is to optimize the economic revenue generated from energy exchange with the main grid, thereby minimizing the operational cost of the hybrid ESS. Since energy exchange with the main grid is possible at all sample instants, there is no requirement for load or generation curtailment procedures. Moreover, there is no need to compute the minimum stored energy value at non-sample instants.

2.6. Resilience MPC: Generic formulation for a single micro-grid

As defined in [4], [6] and [48], when using MPC techniques for microgrid control problems, the state variables are the energy stored in the different ESS which are integrated. Optimizing (44) would, therefore, mean obtaining (50).

Upon analyzing the parameters introduced in (31) and (33), it becomes evident that the resilience parameters are not considered in the cost calculation for the initial iteration. The enhancement in resilience does not, therefore, influence the decision-making of the system at this stage, thus diminishing the potential advantages of having a resilient system.

The critical resilience instants k_{crit} are defined in (37), in which the surplus Υ value is lower for the SH , implying the amount of stored energy is closer to the required energy so as to accomplish the resilience criteria. This study therefore suggests an iterative resolution approach to minimize the impact of said critical points. The proposed system involves two steps: first, optimizing the cost function outlined by [4], without considering resilience, and then incorporating the concept of energy surplus and iterating the procedure in order to maximize minimum surplus energy Υ points. This objective is achieved through the introduction of a new cost function:

$$J_{RES}^{\langle i \rangle} = w_{\Upsilon}^{\langle i \rangle} \cdot \Upsilon^{crit,\langle i \rangle} \quad (45)$$

where w_{Υ} will be the weight factor assigned to the resilience gain, which will be negative in order to maximize the variable. The new cost function will, therefore, be:

$$J^{\langle i \rangle} = J_{NoRes}^{\langle i \rangle} + J_{RES}^{\langle i \rangle} \quad (46)$$

while the general optimum value for any iteration will be:

$$OPT^{\langle i \rangle} = \min J^{\langle i \rangle} \quad (47)$$

And as resilience criteria are not introduced until the second iteration, we could state that:

$$w_{\Upsilon}^{\langle 1 \rangle} = 0 \rightarrow J_{RES}^{\langle 1 \rangle} = 0 \quad (48)$$

$$J^{\langle 1 \rangle} = J_{NoRes}^{\langle 1 \rangle} + J_{RES}^{\langle 1 \rangle} = J_{NoRes}^{\langle 1 \rangle} + 0 = J_{NoRes}^{\langle 1 \rangle} \quad (49)$$

The optimal cost of the first iteration, which will later be used to assess the economic viability of the resilient system, will consequently be:

$$OPT^{<1>} = \min J_{NoRes}^{<1>} \quad (50)$$

and the system will therefore, in the subsequent iterations, be subject to the formula (51) in order to prevent an excessive increase in the operational cost as a result of the introduction of resilience criteria:

$$\begin{aligned} \max J^{<i>} &= OPT^{<1>} \cdot \lambda \\ \forall i &\in [2, n] \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

As defined previously, $OPT^{<1>}$ is obtained from the resolution of (44), and λ is a coefficient created in order to introduce versatility of calculation and to allow the possibility of adding or subtracting weight to/from resilience versus final cost within the calculation, depending on the type of system and the potential consequences of loss of critical load supply. A higher λ value would allow larger deviations from the initial value of $OPT^{<1>}$, implying that the system would be able to find a solution in which the reinforcement of the critical resilience points was greatly increased, but would also mean a higher total cost.

Since $-\infty \leq OPT^{<1>} \leq \infty$, the value of ancillary variable λ is proposed to be:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } OPT^{<1>} \geq 0 &\rightarrow 1 \leq \lambda \leq 1.1 \\ \text{If } OPT^{<1>} < 0 &\rightarrow 0.9 \leq \lambda \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

Parameter λ can also be implemented in order to define an absolute cost margin rather than a relative one by assigning a fixed value to the minimum cost $OPT^{<1>}$, defining Λ :

$$\begin{aligned} \max J^{<i>} &= \min J^{<1>} + \Lambda ; \text{ where } \Lambda \geq 0 \\ \forall i &\in [2, n] \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

The calculations can be iterated successively so as to improve the cost function while maintaining the resilience parameters, until the optimal calculation result is attained in $J^{<n>}$, in which the final cost is that established by (51) or (53).

2.7. Resilience MPC: Critical point enhancement through P2P transactions

Using the work described in [49] as a basis, in the case of having two microgrids working in parallel and connected to the same network, forming a system of subsystems, the exchange of energy between such microgrids can be a decisive tool with which to significantly increase the resilience of the system.

The method proposed can be easily applied to that case by making the following changes:

$$\mathbf{u}^{<i>} = [P_{ch}^{<i>}, P_{dis}^{<i>}, P_{elz}^{<i>}, P_{fc}^{<i>}, P_{pur}^{<i>}, P_{sale}^{<i>}, \Upsilon^{<i>}, \Upsilon^{crit, <i>}, P_{exch}^{<i>}]^T \quad (54)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\delta}^{<i>} = [\delta_{ch}^{<i>}, \delta_{dis}^{<i>}, \delta_{elz}^{<i>}, \delta_{fc}^{<i>}, \sigma_{elz}^{<i>}, \sigma_{fc}^{<i>}, \chi_{elz}^{<i>}, \chi_{fc}^{<i>}, \delta_{exch}^{<i>}]^T \quad (55)$$

where P_{exch} is the new variable for the energy exchanged between microgrids α_1 and α_2 , and δ_{exch} is a logical variable with which to determine whether the microgrids are connected and can, therefore, exchange energy.

In this case, the iteration $I^{<1>}$ would be as described in (56):

$$\begin{aligned} OPT_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_1) &= \min J_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_1) \\ OPT_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_2) &= \min J_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_2) \\ J_{global}^{<1>}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &\leq OPT_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_1) + OPT_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_2) \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

which can be solved in a cooperative mode or a non-cooperative mode in the iteration $I^{<i>}$, as defined in (57) and (58) $\forall i \geq 2$, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} J_{global}^{<i>}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &\leq OPT_{local}^{<i>}(\alpha_1) + OPT_{local}^{<i>}(\alpha_2) \\ J_{global}^{<i>} &\leq J_{global}^{<1>} \cdot \lambda \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

$$\begin{aligned} OPT_{global}^{<i>}(\alpha_1) &\leq OPT_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_1) \\ OPT_{global}^{<i>}(\alpha_2) &\leq OPT_{local}^{<1>}(\alpha_2) \\ J_{global}^{<i>}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &\leq J_{global}^{<1>} \cdot \lambda \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

2.8. Resilience MPC: interaction among three or more microgrids

Although this resolution method is inherently designed for implementation in interconnected P2P microgrid systems, its implementation with more than two microgrids is possible through the application of an iterative procedure in which the benefits of energy exchange between each pair of two microgrids are evaluated in order to determine the optimal pair with which to exchange energy at every instant k of the SH .

In order to evaluate cooperative or non-cooperative P2P benefit between each pair of microgrids $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$, with the total number of microgrids being $N_\alpha \geq 3$, an optimal pair can be found by using (59):

$$\begin{aligned} OPT_{pair}^{<i>} &= \max [OPT_{local}^{<i>}(\alpha_1) + OPT_{local}^{<i>}(\alpha_2) \\ &- OPT_{global}^{<i>}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)] \quad \forall \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

The total number of scenarios N for each iteration $I^{<i>}$ depends exclusively on the number of microgrids N_α involved, as defined in (60):

$$N = (N_\alpha - 1)! \quad (60)$$

The method outlined in Section 2.7 is applied to the chosen pair, while the remaining microgrids continue to operate individually until the conclusion of the current sample period. A new iteration of the proposed method is subsequently computed in order to identify the updated optimal pair of microgrids. The simulation is conducted in accordance with the approach described until the completion of the SH .

3. Results and Discussion

MATLAB[®] and TOMLAB[®] software were used as a solver tool, and numerical simulations were carried out in order to develop and validate the controller. Four simulations were performed with the Resilience MPC Block (initial stage without resilience calculation, resilience with $w_\Upsilon = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $w_\Upsilon = 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Figure 3: Price prediction for day ahead

and $w_{\Upsilon} = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$), which lasted 84 s (each simulation had an average execution time of 21s). The hardware used has the following characteristics: Intel® Core™ i7-10870H CPU at 2.20GHz, 32.0 GB RAM.

Table 2: Components of the microgrids

Grid parameters	
P_{grid_min} : -6kW	P_{grid_max} : 6 kW
Renewable Energy parameters	
PV Pannels: 4kWp	Wind Turbine: 2 kW
Hydrogen ESS parameters	
Electrolyzer: 0,9kW, Tank: 7Nm ³ LOH _{max} : 7Nm ³	Fuel Cell: 0,6 kW LOH _{min} : 3.5Nm ³
Cost _{deg,elz} : 0.0043€/W, Hour = 10000 h ς : 0.23Nm ³ /kW h, CC = 8.22 €/kW h	Cost _{startup,elz} = 0.0082€ Cost _{o&m,elz} = 0.001€/h
Cost _{deg,fc} : 0.0018€/W, Hour = 10000 h ς : 1.320Nm ³ /kW h, CC = 30 €/kW h	Cost _{startup,fc} = 0.018€ Cost _{o&m,fc} = 0.001€/h
$w_{LOH} = 10$	
Batteries ESS parameters	
Battery: $\pm 2,64$ kW; ± 11 kWh Cost _{deg,ch} : 2,9·10 ⁻⁹ €/W ² h	$w_{SOC} = 0.1$ Cost _{deg,dis} : 2,9·10 ⁻⁹ €/W ² h
η_{ch} : 0.90	η_{dis} : 0.95
SOC _{max} = 100%	SOC _{min} = 25%
Resilience Parameters	
$w_{\Upsilon}^{[1]} = 0$	$w_{\Upsilon}^{[2]} = (2 \cdot 10^{-5})$
$w_{\Upsilon}^{[3]} = (4 \cdot 10^{-5})$	$w_{\Upsilon}^{[4]} = (6 \cdot 10^{-5})$
$\lambda = (0,9;1,1)$	

The parameters of both microgrids (α_1, α_2) components are specified in Table 2, and are based on the work of [4]. The time step used for the simulation was $T_s = 1$ hour, and the calculation was performed for $SH = 24$ hours. Energy price data were obtained from the OMIE website (the Spanish Nominated Electricity Market Operator, NEMO) for 15/07/23 (Fig. 3), and were later applied in the forecasting algorithm.

Firstly, the results obtained from the P2P operation of two microgrids without introducing resilience criteria (No E_{RES} No Υ , Iteration $I^{<1>}$) are depicted in Fig. 4. Six graphs were generated, three for each microgrid. Graphs 4.a) and 4.b) portray the power exchange between subsystems for α_1 (grid: P_{grid} , batteries: P_{bat} , hydrogen: P_{H2} , Remaining energy: P_{rem} , and

exchange: $P_{1 \rightarrow 2}$), with graphs 4.d) and 4.e) depicting the same for α_2 . Graphs 4.c) and 4.f) showcase the state of charge of the batteries and the level of hydrogen in the $H2$ tanks for α_1 and α_2 , respectively.

Upon comparing graphs 4 a) and c) with b) and d), it can be observed that the behavior of the system varies slightly with the introduction of energy exchange capacity between microgrids. This primarily results in a decrease in the energy transferred to/from the grid and a slight economic benefit. The behavior of the storage system demonstrates a predominance of battery usage during production peaks.

The calculation is subsequently performed for the same initial parameters, but with the introduction of resilience criteria. Successive iterations, denoted as $I^{<2>}$ to $I^{<4>}$, are implemented, incorporating three different weights for the resilience parameter w_{Υ} : $w_{\Upsilon} = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $w_{\Upsilon} = 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$, and $w_{\Upsilon} = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$. For simplicity, only the results for the first microgrid in these iterations are presented in Figures 5, 6, and 7, in which a vertical line has been drawn at the critical instant $k = 22$ so as to emphasize the differences between iterations.

In Fig. 5, graph c), which corresponds to iteration $I^{<2>}$ with $w_{\Upsilon} = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, a minimal change in the storage trend is observed. It is confirmed that, although the resilience criteria established in (31) are met, the minimum value of Υ is equal to 0 at $k = 22$, as can be seen in graph d) marked with the vertical reference line, thus making this method equal to that which does not include critical point optimization. In this case, and owing to the low weighting of w_{Υ} in the system, the MPC optimizes the storage so as to ensure the lowest economic losses during operation, yet respecting the resilience criteria.

In Fig. 6, graph d), which corresponds to iteration $I^{<3>}$ where $w_{\Upsilon} = 4 \times 10^{-5}$, it can be observed that the minimum value of Υ increases at time period $k = 22$, moving away from 0, but also becomes critical at $k = 21$. The rest of the time it remains similar to the previous iteration. Owing to the increased weighting of w_{Υ} , the MPC considers it more beneficial to increase the storage in order to improve the minimum value of Υ . Instant $k = 21$, which formerly had a greater energy surplus Υ than $k = 22$, is optimized together with its neighboring value. The emergence of a second critical point does not signify a deterioration in the resilience of the system, but rather indicates a heightened demand for energy surplus, as evidenced by the critical values shifting from 0 Wh to 1075 Wh.

In Fig. 7, which corresponds to iteration $I^{<4>}$, where $w_{\Upsilon} = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$, the minimum values of Υ continue to increase at both time periods $k = 21$ and $k = 22$, effectively attenuating the minimum while the variable remains mostly unaffected for the rest of the SH . The increased weighting of w_{Υ} has managed to stabilize Υ during each T_s interval, eliminating critical points without excessively compromising the final cost.

Finally, Table 3 shows a comparison of the LOH, SOC and Υ values obtained in each iteration of the Resilience MPC control block for the first microgrid. The minimum and maximum values for each iteration have been highlighted for the purpose of facilitating comprehension.

It can be observed that most Υ values remain constant for all iterations, while minimum values are progressively enhanced in

Figure 4: Power management without Υ criteria in coop. P2P mode; $I^{<1>}$. Graph a): α_1 standalone mode, power management; Graph b): α_1 P2P mode, power management; Graph c): α_1 P2P mode, Energy storage; Graph d): α_2 standalone mode, power management; Graph e): α_2 P2P mode, power management; Graph f): α_2 P2P mode, Energy storage

order to prevent critical points through the use of an optimization algorithm. Notably, the maximum energy surplus values undergo a significantly lower increase when compared to the minimum ones. Upon analyzing data from iterations 2 and 3, it was noted that there was a 1075 Wh increase for $Min\Upsilon$ (Υ^{crit}) compared to a 287 Wh increase for $Max\Upsilon$, resulting in a 25.0% $Max/Min\Upsilon$ increase ratio. This is attributed to the capability of the algorithm to boost the energy sold, withdrawn or strategically exchanged so as to modulate excess stored energy in order to soften critical points, while successfully minimizing the cost increase from one iteration to the next.

However, upon comparing iterations 3 and 4, it was noted there was a 1145 Wh increase for $Min\Upsilon$ and a 861 Wh increase for $Max\Upsilon$, leading to a 75.2% $Max/Min\Upsilon$ increase ratio. While it is possible to continue iterating the procedure in order to search for higher levels of $Min\Upsilon$, the maximum deviation parameter λ established and the diminishing net difference between Υ_{crit} and the other Υ values for the SH suggest that the difference will become less pronounced with each subsequent increase in the w_Υ variable. Since minimum resilience points have been successfully smoothed, it is considered that further iterative calculations are unnecessary. The ideal operation, in terms of the resilience/cost trade-off, is therefore achieved in the last iteration $I^{<4>}$.

3.1. Comparison of different methods

Several studies, such as [4], address the resilient management of microgrids with hybrid storage systems, suggesting that em-

ploying minimum energy storage constraints E_{RES} suffices to ensure energy supply during disruptive events, as this approach accounts for energy degradation and losses associated with retrieving energy from storage systems to consumption points. However, they overlook the significant influence of the stochastic nature of renewable generation systems. Specifically, a reduction in energy generation at the critical surplus energy (Υ^{crit}) instants may deplete storage systems, leading to a loss of supply to critical charges.

While the mathematical formulation employed by MPC enables the minimization of a cost function using an optimization solver, thus guaranteeing the attainment of the optimal solution, the use of MPC controllers also involves complexities in formulation and requires reliable and, to some extent, pessimistic input data. To date, none of the studies in literature have addressed the stochastic nature of generation regarding minimum stored energy, which may result in the solution obtained being incompatible with the actual operation of the system. Increasing the minimum stored energy profile would not alleviate the problem, as it would also affect instances at which the stored energy greatly surpassed that needed to supply critical loads, resulting in higher operational costs and little benefit.

We qualitatively evaluate the performance of the proposed controller by comparing it with a basic resilience strategy that establishes minimum energy storage constraints (method A) using equations (31) and (32), where $E_{RES}^{<i>}(k) \geq E_{CRIT}^{<i>}(k) \forall k$, simulated by reducing the resilience parameter w_Υ to zero. Then we use the proposed method (method B), employing sur-

Figure 5: Power and Resilience Management $w_\Upsilon = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ in coop. P2P mode (α_1); $I^{<2>}$; Graph a): α_1 standalone mode, power management; Graph b): α_1 P2P mode, power management; Graph c): α_1 P2P mode, Energy storage; Graph d): α_1 P2P mode; Resilience energy balance

Figure 6: Power and Resilience Management $w_\Upsilon = 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ in coop. P2P mode (α_1); $I^{<3>}$; Graph a): α_1 standalone mode, power management; Graph b): α_1 P2P mode, power management; Graph c): α_1 P2P mode, Energy storage; Graph d): α_1 P2P mode; Resilience energy balance

Figure 7: Power and Resilience Management $w_\Upsilon = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ in coop. P2P mode (α_1); $I^{<4>}$; Graph a): α_1 standalone mode, power management; Graph b): α_1 P2P mode, power management; Graph c): α_1 P2P mode, Energy storage; Graph d): α_1 P2P mode; Resilience energy balance

plus energy Υ calculations and critical resilience point enhancement techniques (Υ^{crit}). The results are presented in Table 4, in which method A) is, as explained in Section 3, virtually equivalent to the iteration I^2 shown in Table 3 owing to the extremely low value of w_Υ at said iteration, with the model still heavily prioritizing the economical aspects of the controller.

However, the model clearly indicates significant differences in resilience levels for the optimal solution of method B) at iteration I^4 . Specifically, the optimal economic criterion, which complies with the minimum resilience energy ($\Upsilon = 0$), is

achieved using method A). The increase in the minimum value of Υ^{crit} in method B) indicates that the system is ready to cover situations of higher demand or lower generation. Conversely, the system proposed in method A) would fail to supply the loads of the resilience criteria at critical moments in such scenarios.

The proposed method, which is focused on the optimization of critical moments with a resilience-oriented approach, has significant advantages over previous ones, particularly during critical instants. However, it also poses significant challenges, such as an increased complexity, as the implementation and

Table 3: Comparison between LOH, SOC and Υ obtained by iteration for α_1 in cooperative P2P mode

Iteration	1 (No Υ)		2 ($w_\Upsilon = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$)			3 ($w_\Upsilon = 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$)			4 ($w_\Upsilon = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$)		
	SOC %	LOH %	SOC %	LOH %	Υ (Wh)	SOC %	LOH %	Υ (Wh)	SOC %	LOH %	Υ (Wh)
1	40.0%	50.0%	40.0%	50.0%	3400	40.0%	50.0%	3400	40.0%	50.0%	3400
2	40.0%	50.0%	40.0%	50.0%	3386	40.0%	50.0%	3386	40.0%	50.0%	3386
3	40.0%	50.0%	40.0%	50.0%	3134	40.0%	50.0%	3134	40.0%	50.0%	3134
4	40.0%	50.0%	40.0%	50.0%	3495	40.0%	50.0%	3495	40.0%	50.0%	3495
5	40.0%	50.0%	40.0%	50.0%	3527	40.0%	50.0%	3527	40.0%	50.0%	3527
6	40.0%	50.0%	40.0%	50.0%	3100	40.0%	50.0%	3100	40.0%	50.0%	3100
7	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	5439	58.2%	52.9%	5439	58.2%	52.9%	5439
8	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	5445	58.2%	55.9%	5732	59.0%	55.9%	5803
9	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	4829	58.2%	55.9%	5116	59.0%	55.9%	5187
10	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	4169	58.2%	55.9%	4456	59.0%	55.9%	4528
11	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	3482	58.2%	55.9%	3769	59.0%	55.9%	3841
12	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	2867	58.2%	55.9%	3154	59.0%	58.8%	3513
13	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	2114	58.2%	55.9%	2401	59.0%	61.8%	3046
14	58.2%	52.9%	58.2%	52.9%	3055	58.2%	55.9%	3342	59.0%	64.7%	4274
15	67.4%	55.9%	68.1%	55.9%	6046	67.4%	58.8%	6262	68.1%	67.7%	7194
16	81.8%	58.8%	81.8%	58.8%	7277	81.8%	61.8%	7564	81.8%	70.7%	8425
17	100.0%	61.8%	100%	61.8%	10559	100.0%	64.7%	10846	100.0%	73.6%	11707
18	100.0%	61.8%	100%	61.8%	9342	100.0%	64.7%	9629	100.0%	73.6%	10490
19	100.0%	61.8%	100%	61.8%	7742	100.0%	64.7%	8029	100.0%	73.6%	8890
20	73.3%	55.6%	73.3%	55.6%	3989	73.3%	58.6%	4276	73.3%	67.4%	5137
21	46.7%	50.0%	46.7%	50.0%	840	46.7%	61.2%	1075	49.5%	67.4%	2220
22	25.0% *	50.0% *	29.2%	50.0%	0	40.0%	50.0%	1075	45.5%	56.1%	2220
23	25.0%	50.0%	25.0%	50.0%	2511	25.0%	50.0%	2511	25.0%	50.0%	2511
24	25.0%	50.0%	25.0%	50.0%	2231	25.0%	50.0%	2231	25.0%	50.0%	2231
Υ^{crit}	—	—	—	—	0	—	—	1075	—	—	2220
MAX Υ	—	—	—	—	10559	—	—	10846	—	—	11707

*: Instants where the MIN E_{RES} criterion is not met

management of this method necessitates more sophisticated optimization algorithms and control systems, requiring additional resources, and a higher risk of error, as the accurate identification of critical moments and proper management of the storage system require continuous and precise monitoring in order to avoid potential errors that could affect system resilience, thus highlighting the importance of rigorous supervision.

It is possible to establish that, although the application of surplus energy criteria Υ and minimum point enhancement slightly affects computational cost (19s vs 21s), the difference is not particularly significant from a global perspective, and is not therefore remarkable as a point in favor of either method. However, to continue with the comparison of computational cost using methods such as that employed in [4], which still relies on the resiliency criteria established as method A), with a number $N = 2\alpha SH$ of scenarios, compared to a number i of iterations in the method applied in this work, and considering the general $SH = 24$ instants (and, therefore, 48 scenarios), we can establish that, in most cases, the application of the proposed method will be the most beneficial, as the optimal solution is generally

attained within the first iterations.

It is also possible to state that, while our method provides significant advantages in terms of reducing energy generation stochasticity, its increased program complexity and associated risk of errors at modelization have to be taken into account. The need for the manual programming of successive iterations also introduces an additional probability of error and a time cost.

4. Conclusions

This paper focuses on the development of a new iterative algorithm with which to smooth critical energy resilience points in microgrids by introducing parameters whose purpose is to manage the importance of critical loads along with the use of Model Predictive Control (MPC) techniques.

In recent situations concerning armed conflicts, it has been empirically demonstrated that power generation and supply facilities are critical points targeted by surgical attacks at the onset of conflict, and the importance of the concept of microgrid

Table 4: Comparison between LOH, SOC and Υ obtained for α_1 using method A) (Lower E_{res} limits) and method B) (critical points enhancement techniques) with $w_{\Upsilon} = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Method	A) Limited E_{RES}			B) Υ & $w_{\Upsilon} = 6 \cdot 10^{-5}$		
	SOC %	LOH %	Υ (Wh)	SOC %	LOH %	Υ (Wh)
Instant (k)						
1	40.0%	50.0%	3400	40.0%	50.0%	3400
2	40.0%	50.0%	3386	40.0%	50.0%	3386
3	40.0%	50.0%	3134	40.0%	50.0%	3134
4	40.0%	50.0%	3495	40.0%	50.0%	3495
5	40.0%	50.0%	3527	40.0%	50.0%	3527
6	40.0%	50.0%	3100	40.0%	50.0%	3100
7	58.2%	52.9%	5439	58.2%	52.9%	5439
8	58.2%	52.9%	5445	59.0%	55.9%	5803
9	58.2%	52.9%	4829	59.0%	55.9%	5187
10	58.2%	52.9%	4169	59.0%	55.9%	4528
11	58.2%	52.9%	3482	59.0%	55.9%	3841
12	58.2%	52.9%	2867	59.0%	58.8%	3513
13	58.2%	52.9%	2114	59.0%	61.8%	3046
14	58.2%	52.9%	3055	59.0%	64.7%	4274
15	68.1%	55.9%	6046	68.1%	67.7%	7194
16	81.8%	58.8%	7277	81.8%	70.7%	8425
17	100%	61.8%	10559	100.0%	73.6%	11707
18	100%	61.8%	9342	100.0%	73.6%	10490
19	100%	61.8%	7742	100.0%	73.6%	8890
20	73.3%	55.6%	3989	73.3%	67.4%	5137
21	46.7%	50.0%	840	49.5%	67.4%	2220
22	29.2%	50.0%	0	45.5%	56.1%	2220
23	25.0%	50.0%	2511	25.0%	50.0%	2511
24	25.0%	50.0%	2231	25.0%	50.0%	2231
MIN Υ	—	—	0	—	—	2220
MAX Υ	—	—	10559	—	—	11707

resilience consequently becomes essential. The pursuit of resilience gains significant prominence, especially when considering the optimization of the final cost within an acceptable range.

While forecasting renewable energy generation poses significant challenges owing to its inherent unpredictability, the implementation of an energy surplus and a cost management system mitigates the impact of these uncertainties on the operation of the system. This minimizes the occurrence of outages in critical loads during operation after disruptive events, enhancing the resilience of the system and ensuring a stable supply. However, potential errors in the connections between Energy Storage Systems (ESS) and loads, or within the system components themselves, remain potential points of vulnerability.

The system under study is built upon hybrid generation and storage technologies, incorporating photovoltaic and wind generation systems, along with batteries and hydrogen as ESS. This configuration has the objective of achieving both high power and high energy density capacities. Furthermore, the system distinguishes loads in generic and critical categories. The MPC has been implemented for both standalone microgrid operation mode and Peer-to-Peer (P2P) operation with both cooperative and non-cooperative modes.

MPC controllers were employed in order to effectively coordinate the operation of the different components within the microgrid. This approach also takes into account factors such as degradation and operational costs. As a result, economic revenue is enhanced while the lifespan of the ESS is maximized. The formulation of the MPC algorithm within the MLD framework allows the seamless integration of optimization variables

such as working hours and switching states.

The results obtained confirm that improving minimum resilience points, which are characterized by the value Υ , ensures a more efficient distribution of stored energy while maintaining low operational costs. This feature is particularly relevant for installations with high resilience requirements, such as hospitals, research centers or military bases.

As shown in subsection 3.1 in the comparison between preceding methodologies with which to assess resilience conditions, based on method A) for minimum E_{RES} and method B) for critical instant optimization (summarized in table 4), the readiness for generation or load surplus contingencies is improved with the proposed methodology. Despite its associated computational cost, when compared with the aforementioned minimum storage techniques, it is markedly lower than the computational burden described in more complex works such as that outlined in [4].

The provision of critical loads is, in accordance with the established resilience criteria, ensured by integrating the load consumption profile into the calculations of E_{RES} and Υ . Following the inclusion of these criteria in successive iterations, these loads are never at risk of being left without supply. In the final iteration, it is possible to state that the system is capable of maintaining a greater number of loads in the event of a disruption, all while staying within the specified cost range thanks to the inclusion of parameter λ . A significant enhancement has consequently been achieved.

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